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Assessment of the Effect of Seasonal Honeybee Management on Honey Production of Ethiopian Honeybee (*Apis mellifera*) in Modern Beekeeping in Jimma Zone

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

Ethiopia has substantial potential in beekeeping with rich flora, proper ecological conditions and existence of large bee colonies. However, modern beekeeping in study area is still faced with challenges in respect to lack of bee management skill, colony absconding and low honey production. The study was conducted in Jimma Zone where modern beekeeping has been practiced since 40 years. For the study three districts (Kersa, Goma and Gera) were purposively selected depending upon the existence of large number of modern beekeeping. A total of 75 beekeepers engaged in modern beekeeping were contacted and interviewed. Visual assessment of apiaries and internal inspection of suspected colonies were carried out to harmonize the relevant information noted by respondents. Interview on beekeepers characteristics, seasonal bee management practices of modern beekeeping, bee forage flowering seasons, bee management constraints and honey production were collected and analyzed. The result revealed that 62.7% modern beekeeping in the study area is based on inappropriate colony management practices and characterised predominately by high absconding and low honey yield despite the abundant bee forage potential in the study areas. Inappropriate skill bee management practices, colony absconding, poor design of modern beehives, low honey yield and bee pests are the main problems that impede the full use of apiculture resources in the study area. Interventions in modern beekeeping should be focused on empowering beekeepers with skills through ensuring availability of improved beekeeping technologies with standard seasonal bee management practices should be strengthened.

Key words: Modern beekeeping, bee management, colony absconding, honey production.

INTRODUCTION

Beekeeping is an important, sustainable, integral agricultural and forestry activity under the rural development program (Munthali, 1992; Thomas *et al*, 2002; Lietaer, 2009). It provides nutritional, economic, and ecological security (Masuku, 2013). Ethiopia has considerable potential in beekeeping with rich flora, good ecological conditions and existence of large amount of colonies (Fichtl and Admasu, 1994). Ten million honeybee colonies existed in Ethiopia and one million farmer beekeepers engaged in which (95.5%) in traditional (4.3%) in intermediate and (0.2%) modern beekeeping. Moreover, 42,000 metric tons of honey and 5000 metric tons of beeswax produced per year in Ethiopia (Beyene and Davide, 2007). However, the sector has not yet sufficiently utilized the rich apicultural resources possibly resulted from lack of adequate skill on improved beekeeping management practices.

The low yield of honey and other beekeeping products resulted from insufficient management practices and lack of adequate beekeeping training (Bhusal and Thapa, 2005; Masuku, 2013). Pollen and nectar are a resource need for honeybees available only during certain periods. When surplus food source are available it is known as honey flow season. In contrast during dearth period there will be scarcity of food. Local bee flora skill and specific seasonal colony management plans play a key role in transforming beekeeping sector (Thomas *et al*, 2002; Kumar *et al*, 2013; Tesfa *et al*, 2013). Productive beekeeping involves understanding of the yearly colony cycles and carrying out seasonal bee management operations to build colonies to its maximum population during the main nectar flow and to survive the dearth period to assure the greatest possible return (Brown, 2001; Thomas *et al*, 2002). Proper seasonal colony management practices would greatly improve colony performance and honey yields (Haloua, 1989).

Jimma Zone has considerable potential in beekeeping with rich flora, good ecological conditions, existence large colonies population and modern beehive. However, it is characterized by high absconding rate and low honey

production. In the country in general and in the study areas in particular, no studies have been conducted to assess the effects of seasonal colony management on honeybee colonies performance and honey production.

METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted in Jimma Zone in Ethiopia during the main flowering season of the year (April to May 2012). Three (3) districts (Kersa, Goma and Gera) where modern beekeeping principally dominated were purposively selected out of the existing districts in the zone. Interviews using structure questioners and observation through colonies inspection were used as research tool. Beekeeping households, district and zonal experts were involved in interviews. The colonies inspection schedule was used to record relevant information noticed by households and experts during the fieldwork. A total of 75 modern beekeepers, 25 beekeepers from each district was randomly selected and used for the study. To be selected in the study, one had engaged in modern beekeeping for at least 5 years and has an established apiary with a minimum of five occupied modern beehives. Seasonal honeybee management practices, major flowering plant, production problems as well as harvesting skills and bee product marketing were collected and analyzed. A number of open-ended questions were also asked so as to get the improved beekeeping information without restricting the respondents. The data were processed using the SPSS package Version 14 and descriptive statistics such as mean, percentage table, crosstabs, graphs, and frequencies were used to analyze the data.

Figure 1. Location map showing the study areas of modern beekeeping in Jimma zone, Ethiopia

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Characteristic of beekeepers

The results in table 1 revealed that 37.5% of beekeepers engaged in modern beekeeping had the age range between 31 and 40 years and 28 % had an age between 41 and 50 years. The analysis of survey result further revealed that 30.7% of the respondents have received primary education, 18.7% received secondary education, and 22.7 % has no education table 1.

Table 1. Characteristic of beekeepers

Age (years)	Number of beekeepers	Percentage
15 -30	18	26.6
31 - 40	28	37.3
41 - 50	21	28
51 - 60	3	4
Above 61	3	4
Education of level		
1-6 (primary)	23	30.7
7-10 (Secondary)	21	28
11-12 (Level)	14	18.7
No education	17	22.7

Type of bee hives

According to Jimma Zone Livestock Development and Health Agency Offices, 37,157 modern beehives have been distributed between 2002 and 2012 and 2,456,625 occupied traditional hives existed in the zone. All interviewed beekeepers engaged in modern beekeeping as well as traditional beekeeping. All of the traditional hives are made locally and not appropriate to open to manipulate and harvest ripen and pure honey as a result, beekeepers failed to harvest sufficient honey from the traditional hive (8-13 kg of crude honey). Crude honey is mixed with wax and the largest buyers are middlemen out of the beekeeping community.

A total number of modern beehive enumerated during survey in beekeepers apiary were 1087 of which 834 were colonized and the rest 253 without bees due to colony absconding at different time for different reasons (Table 2). The total number of traditional beehive colonized were 2160 where as 344 were without bees (Table 2). The management style of traditional beekeeping system is different from modern beekeeping in the study area. The survey result shows that 74% in Kersa, 68% in Goma and 83% in Gera practiced only one harvest by taking traditional beehives down from the tree and makes all traditional hives empty of bees during dearth seasons. In the next flowering season beekeepers use different smoking attractants and hanged again on the tree and is difficult to get more than one harvest per year because of the time required for bees to set combs and store honey. However, the rest of beekeepers in each district practiced careful handling of bees under their roof, in this case, beekeepers could be used for more than one time harvesting.

Regarding to modern beekeeping, beehives empty of bees were 19% in Kersa, 26% in Goma and 23% in Gera of total counted in modern beehives in the districts. This showed that absconding due to inappropriate colony management was the major constraints in the districts as a result, beekeepers failed to produce sufficient amount of honey, regardless of apiculture potential in study area. Proper bee management practices such as hive inspection, pest control and provision of water must be followed to overcome dearth period to enhance colony performance such as reduced absconding, improved colony strength and higher hive yields (Wilson 2006 Kumar et al, 2013).

Table 2. Traditional and modern beehives with and without bees

Districts	Number traditional hive with bees	Number of traditional hive without bees	Number of modern hive with bees	Number of modern hive without bees
Kersa	700	142	280	66
Goma	620	89	400	141
Gera	840	113	154	46
Total mean	2160	344	834	253

All beekeepers owned Zander type modern beehive and the mean number of beehives colonized with bees in modern hive varies from beekeepers to beekeepers. The highest mean is in Goma district (18) and the least mean is in Gera district (7.7). The mean number of traditional hives is owned by beekeepers is highest (42) in Gera district and lowest (31) in Goma district Table 3.

Table 3. Mean number of traditional and modern hive colonized with bees

District	Mean traditional hive	Mean modern hive	Minimum traditional hive	Maximum traditional hive	Minimum modern hive	Maximum modern hive
Kersa	35	12.0	12	120	5.00	18.00
Goma	31	18.0	10	85	6.00	60.00
Gera	42	7.7	12	140	5.00	14.00
Total	36	12.5	10	140	5.00	60.00

Seasonal bee management in modern beekeeping

Honeybee management practice is the regular inspection of colonies to assess the status of brood condition, giving additional hive super for expansion of colony during flowering, distinguishing and harvesting of ripe honey, space reduction, feeding and maintaining colonies during dearth periods and detection and control of bee pests which enhances colony performance such as reduced absconding, improved colony strength and higher hive yields (Thomas et al, 2002; Farinde et al, 2005; Wilson, 2006; Okwee-Acai, 2010). Detail assessments of seasonal colony management revealed that 28% of respondents put additional hive without inspecting the internal condition of the colonies and harvested less than 19.5 kg of honey. Most respondents (62.7%) keep additional super on colonies without reducing and feeding and visited the colonies twice a year only at harvesting time (Figure 2 and 4). Leaving too much empty frames with combs during dearth periods causes a problem of wax moth leads to high loss of wax and honey (Curtis, 1985).

Only 16.6% of respondents have got practical training in improved beekeeping by different NGO's and district livestock development agents. The practically trained beekeepers generally have good knowledge of the beekeeping management practices with modern techniques. They carried out dearth period bee management (timely feeding, timely super reducing and bee pest management) and active period bee management (comb renewal, swarm prevention, timely super adding to provide enough space to store nectar, and timely inserting queen excluder) (Figure 2). The survey result showed that the beekeepers who follow the standard management techniques harvested more than 25 kg of honey per harvesting season. Very few (5%) of practically trained beekeepers in the study areas fixed queen excluder at the hive entrance for a few days after transferring colonies from traditional hives to modern hive to prevent the queen not to abscond from new modern hives (Figure 3).

Figure 2. Seasonal colony management practices

Figure 3. Queen excluder at the hive entrance to avoid absconding of the newly established colony

Figure 4: Modern beehives with its supers not reduced for the last 1-3 years

Honey harvesting

The frequency and amount of honey harvested varied depending on seasonal colony management practices depending upon flowering condition of major bee forage and number of modern beehive (Kajobe, et al, 2009). As the respondents in the study area indicated, there was significant difference ($P < 0.05$) in honey yield in modern bee hive among districts. However, there was no significant difference ($p = 0.15$) in honey yield in traditional beehive. As could be observed from Table 5, the amount of honey harvested in one harvesting season was 22.4 ± 7.8 , 27 ± 7.6 , and 20 ± 6.4 kgs in modern hives and 8.7 ± 2.5 , 10.3 ± 3.3 , and 9.5 ± 2.5 kgs in traditional hives in Kersa, Goma and Gera respectively. According to the survey results most (73.3%) of the respondents harvested honey two times a year (October to November and May to June), 18% of the respondents harvested honey only once a year (only October to November) and 8% of the respondents harvested three times a year (October to November, January and May to June). Similar result was reported by Chala et al (2013) that honey was harvested once or twice and even three times in the same zone depending upon the seasonal bee management skills and flowering potential of the area.

The spearman correlation test result revealed that amount of honey harvested was positively and significantly influenced by the good seasonal bee management practiced ($p = 0.73$). According to the survey result 65.3% of beekeepers harvested less than 25 kg of honey which is less than the country average reported (Kibebew and Dereje, 2006) and the rest 34.7% harvested more than 25 kg of honey from Zander hive. Masuku (2013) also found significant influence on the relationship of colony management and honey production that beekeepers who have better bee management skills tends to produce higher honey production in modern hive. The results showed that 16% of the respondents did not know when honey is matured to harvest. This showed that there is a shortage of appropriate technical assistance for beekeepers to detect when honey is matured in the study area.

Table 5. Mean, minimum and maximum honey harvested per colony per one harvesting season in modern and traditional hives

Districts	Statistics	Honey harvested from modern hive in kg	Honey harvest from traditional hive in kg
Kersa	Mean± SD	22.4±7.8	8.7±2.5
	Minimum	10.00	5.00
	Maximum	40.00	13.50
Goma	Mean± SD	27±7.6	10.3±3.3
	Minimum	15.00	4.00
	Maximum	38.00	15.00
Gera	Mean± SD	20±6.4	9.5±2.5
	Minimum	12.00	5.00
	Maximum	34.00	13.00
Total	Mean± SD	23±7.8	9.5±2.8

Honey plants and their flowering season

Beekeepers reported that they depended on many kinds of flowering plants including trees, shrubs, undergrowth and different kinds of flowering crops and weeds. Some of the abundant honey plants, with their scientific and local names, and flowering seasons are given based on field observations and local knowledge of beekeepers in Table 6. During the survey, it was observed that all beekeepers (100%) practiced backyard beekeeping and engaged in the plantation and preservation of native bee flora important for agro-forestry and coffee shade. This encourages beekeepers to be allied with the current efforts of watershed and agro-forestry conservation and rehabilitation programme (Munthali, 1992; Lietaer, 2009; Tolera, 2014).

Table 6. Important bee forage plants, shrubs and weeds and their flowering periods

	Botanical Name	Common name	Blooming period
1	<i>Vernonia amygdalina</i>	Girawa	Jan-February
2	<i>Croton macrostachys</i>	Bisana	April-May
3	<i>Coffea arabica</i> (Coffee)	Buna	Feb-March
4	<i>Cordia africana</i>	Wanza	Oct-January depending on rain fall
5	<i>Gizotia scabira</i>	Mech	September
6	<i>Bidens pachyloma</i>	Kelo	September- Oct
7	<i>Grevillea robusta</i>	Temenja enchet	April-may
8	<i>Eucalyptus spp</i>	Baherzaf	April-June
9	<i>Scheffleria abyssinica</i>	Geteme	March- May

Experienced beekeepers familiar with the plants that produce nectar or/and pollen, when it blooms and how long they remain in blooming. According to the beekeepers view, most important bee flowering shrubs, crops and weeds flowered between September and November and most important plants flowered in March and May and some in January. In Kersa and Goma districts, the major honey season is between September and October from *Gizotia scabira*, *Bidens pachyloma*, *Cordia africana* and other weedy species. In Gera district, the major honey season is between May and June from *Croton macrostachys* and *Scheffleria abyssinica* flower, dominantly grown in the area. Honey produced in May to June is usually mixed with honey from coffee flower. A good beekeeping area is one in which honey and pollen plants grow abundantly and with a relatively long blooming season. It requires the presence of appropriate crops and plants to favor foraging. Many agro-forestry tree species were found in gardens of farmers and were good sources of forage for the beekeepers (Kajobe, et al, 2009).

Factors affecting modern beekeeping

The most important factors that hinder the modern beekeeping were similar in all study areas. The beekeepers explained the problems they have experienced since they started modern beekeeping that needs attention by the

intervention of concerned agencies. The problems that were of great concern of the respondents were related to the lack of skill on bee management (70%), colonies absconding (56.6%), poor designing of locally constructed modern beehive (31%), honeybee pests (43.7%), harvesting unripe honey (30.3%) and pricing fluctuation of honey (40.6%) (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Major factor affecting modern beekeeping

Related problems were identified by (Chala et al, 2013 Masuku, 2013 and Tolera, 2014) that lack of skill in modern bee management contributed to colony absconding and low honey production. Other factors that affect colony included pests and predators that either lead colonies to abscond or to die. The most threatening pest and predator reported were wax moth and ants respectively. The results showed that 21% beekeepers practicing ant protection using plastic tube (figure 6). During internal observation of colonies, 18% of the inspected colonies were very weak and affected by wax moth (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Traditional ant protection and wax moth affected combs

Another problem that was of great concern was price fluctuation of honey in the area. Beekeepers sold their honey as early as possible in the harvesting seasons which tempt to harvest and sell unripe honey. The time of honey harvesting throughout the districts is similar (October to November and May to June and sometimes January). This contributed to low prices being offered for beekeepers honey. The price of honey was subjected to fluctuate with the highest price of 80 Ethiopian birr for pure honey and 55 birr for crude honey per kg in the dry seasons coupled with the time of wedding and cultural ceremonies in April. The lowest price of honey was reported during honey harvesting time in October to November and June with 40 Ethiopian birr for pure honey and 22 birr for crude honey per kg (Figure 7). Lack of market information on honey prices coupled with problems of honey brokers contributed to low prices of honey in the area. The main buyers of honey are the local brewers (17%), local consumers (19.5%) and middlemen out of the beekeeping community (64.5%). When districts were compared in terms of honey price per

kilogram, there was no significant difference ($P < 0.05$) for both crude and table honey. Chala et al (2013) also found related result that honey price is not significantly different among different districts of Jimma Zone.

Representatives of districts and zonal experts that are involved in beekeeping identified more or less the same problems with beekeepers. They particularly stated lack of inappropriate bee management skills, colony absconding and low production of honey as the main problems.

Figure 7. Price fluctuations of honey across the months of the year

Figure 8: Freshly harvested honey waiting for market

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The productive efficiency of beekeeping is the cumulative effect of available bee forage, its flowering phenology and seasonal colony management skills following the seasonal cycle of flower. However, the potential of beekeeping in study areas is yet to be tapped to increase honey production. This is because of lack of knowledge on available bee forage resources, its flowering seasons and poor seasonal colony management, which leads to colony absconding, low honey production, high pests and predators. Beekeepers need to gain skill in modern beekeeping management in order to improve their seasonal bee management practices to increase honey production. This could be done through improving the technical efficiency of respective extension workers and beekeepers through training and practical demonstrating of modern beekeeping. Model modern beekeeping demonstration should be established in existing Farmer Training Centers (FTC's) in close liaison with district Livestock Development and Health Agency so that beekeepers could learn how to manipulate seasonal bee management. Beekeepers should be organized in to cooperative to establish honey collection centers for fair bee product marketing.

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